

The Ethnographic Research in Anthropology its Challenges and Limitations

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Academic Writings (SSAW 712)

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Abstract:- This paper provides a clear understanding of the challenges faced by Social Science ethnographers while conducting ethnographic research under Social and Cultural Anthropology. An ethnographic study is considered one of the most integral methodological tools in Anthropology, but due to diverse understanding of this process, at times the essence is misled. The paper describes the trends of the challenges and limitations, which varies according to the research topic, contexts methods, and fieldwork site. This paper also tries to underline the different confrontations faced by the various other disciplines, which are researched linking ethnography as their means of study. This paper tries to interpret and analyze the information through an explorative and descriptive approach. In Anthropology, Ethnography research can be considered an effective and efficient methods as long as the ethics of the ethnography is well understood and well implemented. The outcome of the paper will try to interpret and analyze the possible challenges while in the field or while interpreting the data by the ethnographers while carrying out the ethnographic research.

Keywords:- *Ethnographic, Research, Qualitative, Challenge, and Anthropology.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The literal meaning of ethnography is “a portraying of people.” (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2007). It aims to describe what is happening in a particular setting together with the participant’s perspectives on these events. In general understanding, it is to interpret particular cultural groups or ethnic groups setting from the perspective of both researcher and locals focusing holistic approach is described as ethnographic research. It focuses on all of the events of how a particular social group operates and accomplishes this by means of direct observation and interviews with key participants. It is also referred to as interpretive research as it attempts to explain people’s behavior in terms of the beliefs, which people hold, about their behavior. Ethnography is a written description of a particular culture (the customs, beliefs, and behavior) based on information collected through fieldwork. (Harris & Johnson 2000). Ethnographic methods include intensive fieldwork particularly participant observation by a single or group of ethnographers, who live with them and live like them. This method provides an accurate and deep understanding of the

way people live, about their profession, how they use things to what they need in their everyday or professional lives. The most commonly used techniques for the methods of data collection under ethnographic research are observations, video diaries, photographs, contextual interviews, and analysis of artifacts.

Singleton and straits (2005) have identified five major steps of ethnographic research, which are, problem formulation, selecting a research setting, gaining access, presenting oneself, and gathering and recording information. The method was first applied in educational research in the 1950s, where ethnographers enter classrooms, schools, and family groups or community settings to identify inside knowledge by asking different questions to different stakeholders of education. Thus, the characteristics of ethnographic research are a mixture of historical, observational, and interview methods. In this method, the researcher usually observes target users in their natural, real-world setting, and not in an artificial environment of a lab or focus group. It allows for collecting data in a realistic or naturalistic setting in which people act naturally, focusing on both verbal and non-verbal behaviors. It is longitudinal in nature (changes with time may be observed). It provides detailed and rich data and information for further investigation and writing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the literature review online (mostly) scholarly sources on the challenges and limitations of ethnographic study, its methodological process, and qualitative research have been included. It provides an overview of the current knowledge in ethnographic research as a subject. Some of the theoretical methods that are relevant also exist. For citation and reference APA (America Psychological Association) 7th edition has been followed.

The researcher Reeves et al., (2013), has revealed Ethnography to be a type of qualitative research that gathers information through observations, interviews, and documentary data to produce details and comprehensive accounts of different social phenomena. And they further add that the use of ethnographic research in medical education has produced a number of insightful accounts of its roles, functions, and difficulties in the preparation of medical students for clinical practice. The journal also explores the limitations of work undertaken in a medical

education context, which requires methodological refinement to enhance the quality of future ethnographic work in the field.

Ethnography studies are one of the earliest qualitative approaches in Anthropology that have always based its study based its study diving into its native population, immersing into the depth of conversation characterized by the participant observation. This allows the Ethnographers to dig out the real issues that they intend to find, "Although it has been argued that ethnography is purely a data collection method, epistemologically it is about immersion in a culture and the artistry of seeing, learning and interpreting reality by engaging with participants, either overtly or covertly in their natural environment." (Smith, 2017). This research often analyses the information at the micro-level and is the continuous process of involving the participants in their natural environment.

In Ethnographic research design, from the perspective of experimenting with the data, a number of important problems have been identified. There are seven major identified issues and their inter-relationships with each other are connected with their methodological aspect. The core-identified issues are the Complexity of test development; Variability of methods; resource intensiveness; subjectivity and culture; inter-test comparability; lack of clear common standards for metrics; and finally context and industrial acceptance (Philip, Ben, Steve, 2009). Unless the above issues are not resolved through a properly structured methodological approach, then maintaining high levels of performance is not obtained in ethnographic research design.

Consequently, within ethnographic studies, there seem to be dilemmas in the findings of movement or mobility studies. "By interlinking migration, transport and tourism studies, the new mobilities scholarship addresses emerging challenges and discourse concerning environmental development, justice and security issues at local and global levels." (D'Andrea, Ciolfi & Gray, 2011). In the contemporary conditions of globalization of movement, mobilities seem to carry a heavier empirical and epistemological weight in mutually limiting social, material and cultural domains which previously seen as autonomous. While micro-sociological and phenomenological approaches are predominant in the scholarship, large-scale studies on mobility not to tend to systematically analyze research frameworks used in the process of knowledge production. Therefore, the multi-scalar and critical methodologies are necessary for further expanding the analytical and interventional possibilities of a mobilities research agenda.

One of the effective methods for collecting data in Ethnographic research is Participant Observation. It has been used in a variety of disciplines for collecting data about people, processes, and cultures in qualitative research. Marshall and Rossman (1989) define observation as "the systematic description of events, behaviors, and artifacts in the social setting chosen for study" (p.79). But there are several other anthropological researchers who claimed that there are numerous limitations involved in using observation

as a tool for data gathering. Kawulich (2005) states, "Participant observation is conducted by a biased human who serves as the instrument for data collection; the researcher must understand how his/her gender, sexuality, ethnicity, class, and theoretical approach may affect observation, analysis, and interpretation."

Ethical consideration is a significant element that needs to be considered by Ethnographers. These ethics include taking consent from respondents and assuring their privacy and information will be maintained and fully addressed (Rashid, Caine, and Goetz, 2015). However, due to negligence and taking things for granted this does not happen. Either the researcher underestimates taking consent or published personal information more than permitted. At times the researchers are so submerged in the community through participation and observation that they end with an ethical dilemma. Gajjar (2013), explains that everyone recognizes certain common ethical standards, but the problem is with individuals' interpretation, application, and balance of these norms in different ways in light of their own values and life experience. There are a range of difficulties and challenges claiming ethnographic research. In this connection, Hammersley (2006), suggests that:

(...) Issues include: how ethnographers define the spatial and temporal boundaries of what they study; how they determine the context that is appropriate for understanding it; in what senses ethnography can be or is virtual rather than actual; the role of interviews as a data source; the relationship between ethnography and discourse analysis; the tempting parallel with imaginative writing; and, finally, whether ethnography should have, or can avoid having, political or practical commitments of some kind, beyond its aim of producing value- relevant knowledge.

Rudkin (2002), adds that the "Key limitations in ethnographic research identified are the limiting factors of language, the morphing effects of context, imperfections of the researcher, and ethical considerations surrounding the verification and ownership of data."

According to Wilson (1997), there is a growing in the use of Anthropological techniques in natural and social science research. To conduct such qualitative or ethnographic research we need ample trainings and experience. Because ethnographic methodology differs significantly from the research approaches more commonly used in other facilities, it is important to clarify its rationale and data collection process. It is essential to understand the ways in which ethnographic research differs from other approaches because they represent fundamentally different claims about the nature of human behavior and the best ways of coming to understand it. Ethnography discerns both the depth and complexity of social structures and relations, (Jeffrey & Troman, 2013).

Accordingly, Berg (2008), discloses how international borders provide fertile but challenging ground for anthropological research. Extending ethnographic inquiries to a multiplicity of sites due to mobility and displacement

worldwide, the researcher faced difficulties. And when doing ethnography of transactional spaces and subjectivities we are faced with a number of practical, methodological, and analytical challenges not encountered in single-sited ethnography. A real challenge with multi-sited fieldwork is that the researcher has less time at each individual site and with each localized population, thus having fewer opportunities to “get to know” people and their social worlds and to establish more profound social relationships, in ways that allow us access to more existential fields of experience.

Hence, the ability to see how people are constructing themselves, their families, their neighborhoods, localities, communities, and the connections among them is more limited. This limitation itself must be approached analytically and addressed directly through varied and versatile research practices implemented for their appropriateness to particular sites, questions, and situations, such as team-based research, fieldwork in transit (moving with migrating individuals and groups), or other interdisciplinary work.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the research methodology applied while conducting research. Due to COVID-19, it is almost impossible to visit sites and acquire desirable primary data. Some of the data collection tools and techniques like focused group discussion – FGD and participant observation are key tools for gathering information in qualitative research that cannot be executed. Because this needs a physical presence in the study site and face-to-face interaction with the respondents. Therefore, an online questionnaire schedule with the expertise of the researcher and research document analysis will be applied as a means of collecting data for interpretation. As a source of qualitative data a few experts, ethnographers; researchers; anthropologists and learners will be selected, which is the limitation of this study.

➤ *Online Questionnaire Schedule*

The research process is incomplete without the collection of data. There are several methods that are involved in the collection of primary data. And on the effective means of collecting data is an online questionnaire schedule. Gathering data online is gaining popularity as it saves time and money. And most importantly the desired information can be generated without visiting the site. In Anthropology studies especially in ethnographic research it is important to visit the study area, but in situations like Corona Pandemic, online methods can prove effective tools and the desired outcomes can be accomplished.

There will be few sets of questions asked to the experts; Anthropologists; and researchers on the challenges and limitations that they experienced while undertaking ethnographic research. This conduction of research will be online through the use of the Internet. And the relevant information shall be obtained. This is an effective and efficient way to accumulate primary data from the

respondent. The collected data will be closely examined through qualitative approach.

➤ *Research Document Analysis*

Document analysis is an important method in social research. In it previously published documents, literature, and journals on the relevant and related topic will be closely examined and will be analyzed for the results. It is a type of qualitative research in which documents are interpreted by the researcher to provide a meaningful understanding of his/her research topic. In its already published journals; research articles; thesis; dissertations; books and newspapers will be thoroughly analyzed and taken into consideration. For analyzing information from these resources systematic planning procedures have to be followed. First of all, we have to create a list of texts to analyze and explore. Secondly, these obtained documents have to ensure no cultural and linguistic barriers. The researcher further has to develop strategies to ensure credibility and ethical consideration like confidential information has to be taken seriously.

➤ *Study Method*

A qualitative research method will be adopted to carry out this research.

IV. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This chapter deals with the evaluation of results and outcomes obtained from the online questionnaire and the analysis of the document. Data obtained from the research method has been deeply interpreted and analyzed through the qualitative data analysis process.

➤ *Research Code of Conduct*

Ethnographic research deals with ethnic people, groups, and communities. Since it is about the social norms and values that they exercise while socializing in their own community. Therefore, a set of moral principles and values has to adhere to in order to maintain the integrity of the research. A researcher has to be morally responsible and ethically sound in following up the research code of conduct. And the researcher should conduct research without harming any component of the community.

But in most academic and general research such ethical considerations are not strictly followed or taken seriously. A researcher either underestimates the community to seek consent or tries organizing the confidentiality of the respondent or does not realize the importance of maintaining all of these recorded documents in writing. While in a community, a researcher should speak well; behave well, and should not use any toxic substance that puts people in shame. And moreover, privacy related to the community's behavior and practice was found not taken into consideration.

Protecting the human subject is an integral aspect of any research. Protection of human subjects includes a historical, psychological, and health-related aspect of the respondent. Since this is a sensitive subject and normally

research is conducted only after preparing and approving the research code of conduct from the concern institution. But this hardly happens in most academic research. How to protect the privacy and emotions of the respondent is not literally considered. Those who try to adopt also do not completely comply with the complete procedures of ethical consideration, as it should be. As a consequence, people's personal information is leaked and publicly disclosed without taking proper consent from them. This way respondents lose faith in the researcher and it impacts the upcoming researcher who has planned to organize research in the same area with the same people.

➤ *As a Social Science Researcher, there are Many Ethical Issues that Needs to be Considered:*

- Informed consent
- Confidentiality
- Anonymity
- Aware to harm (Physical and socio-cultural)
- Responsible to institutional rules and regulations
- Aare to plagiarism
- Appropriate acknowledging
- Concern to community interpretation (Acharya, 2018)

➤ *Ethnographic Research in Special Scenarios (in Violent Environments; Natural Disasters and Transnational Research)*

The most challenging task in research is to conduct research in a violent environment, natural disaster setting, and between the populations of different countries. Violence is a social phenomenon and is common in every society. Very few scholars prefer to conduct research in such a situation. Because of the fact that it is highly risky and unsafe to handle comprehensive research in such a scenario. There are very limited researches that are found conducting regarding such furious settings. Such violence in society can be man-made or natural, political, institutional, religious outbreak, civil war, or conflict. Very wise and careful consideration has to undertake while designing this type of research. It has to be well articulated on the policies and best practices in order to conduct safe and ethical conduct and collection of violent data. Therefore, it is very challenging to conduct research in a violent environment. In some of the violent situations if it is handled improperly the safety and even the lives of the respondent and interviewer may be at risk. Even the targeted respondent experience traumatic stress and psychological problems related to violence and disaster. For a while, they will not be fit to participate in the research process. Warden, Tara (2013), the authors delineate the risks of emotional trauma in ethnographic research working with vulnerable groups in a dangerous environment. The writers present their reflexive analysis during ethnographic research experience and aim to raise awareness about the acute emotional consequences of conducting research with marginalized populations in violent contexts. They further explain,

“Ethnographers, as tools of data collection, are uniquely positioned in a paradoxical relationship between intense immersion and objective distance from research and

participants. This relationship can be particularly intense when researching hidden or marginalized communities in violent contexts. Yet, the emotional consequences of research on the researcher are rarely discussed and little literature exists. When emotions in research are revealed, researchers can be confronted with stigma surrounding issues of subjectivity, "going native" and implications of failed research”.

Actually, disaster research allows people in the field to advance in the existing preparedness, response, and recovery practices. It is important to study earlier about the disaster-prone region to wholly prepare and safeguard the lives.

During natural calamities, it is people and their ecosystem on which they are dependent and largely impacted by terrible consequences. In it, many people suffer from psychological issues caused by the loss of property, possessions, and most importantly the loss of their loved ones.

There are additional risks for survivors to participate in a research study. Researchers must be aware that some populations are more likely to experience greater risk as participants especially those who are socially and medically vulnerable. Thus, researchers should carefully design in order to minimize the possible risks to the participants. There are numerous challenges attached when involved in ethnographic research in disaster regions, that includes physical harm, inconvenience, legal problems, economic hardship, psychological discomfort, loss of dignity, and unwanted media involvement.

Transnational research is a comparative and comprehensive research approach between the people of two or more countries. Such research concludes and provides a wider range of knowledge of various regions between or among the countries. Now there is a growing trend of conducting transnational research in the context of a similar socio-cultural setting. At times social life crosses and transcends the boundaries in different ways. Issues like relative human rights, gender studies, and social values are collaboratively studied across borders. But this multi-national study has legal setbacks; problems in the generalization of results/findings and is time-consuming, which is challenging to conduct in academic research.

➤ *Describing Cultural Complexities*

Culture includes a vastness of human behaviors, patterns, and interactions. It encompasses religion, food, what we wear, and, marriage, music, Symbols, and people's beliefs. Culture is an acquisition process and is transmitted through the socialization process. In conclusion, a culture is a set of rules to drive the community as a whole.

Culture is dynamic and keeps changing. Thus, its transformation face cannot be understood superficially only through peripheral scratch. A few weeks or months spent with a certain ethnic group does not completely build our holistic understanding of that particular community. In academic research, it is mostly seen that a researcher hardly

spent a month time with the people, and during this limited time frame is not sufficient for any researcher to gain deeper insight and knowledge about their cultural practice. There has to be intimacy and healthy rapport relation and in order to have this relationship, we need to invest more quality time not only in collecting data but also in developing relationships. Then only one can win the confidence of the people, only after which factual data are obtained from the respondent. The dynamism of a culture has to be understood and interpret accordingly.

Though in every society culture is observed but the components of the cultural practice in every society are different. Therefore, a researcher has to be fully aware and has to be educated about this variance of cultural observation from place to place is different. The pre-occupied mindset and stereotype assumption obstruct cultural understanding as a consequence real findings and outcomes will not be obtained.

Researchers are challenged with many social issues while carrying out their research with people in complex-cultural arenas. There are many cultural barriers faced by ethnographers, some of which are mentioned below: 1) the possibility of cultural biasness; 2) Understanding their local language; 3) the ability of the researcher to endure the situations in which the subject is being studied; 4) presumptions about inferior and superior culture; 5) a wide range of theoretical understanding; 6) quality to adopt local culture and 7) proper rapport building with the locals.

➤ *Problems with Sampling and Interpretation of Qualitative Data in Ethnographic Research:*

Usually, ethnographic research doesn't generate quantifying data. The obtained data are qualitative and non-numeric. There are both drawbacks and advantages of qualitative data. The advantages of qualitative data are, it provides a deep and detailed understanding of the subject. But at the same time, it also carries limitations. One of which is with the 'sample size.' For example, if there are 200 households in a particular community, and if a researcher takes a sample of only 10 households and 190 households. This raises the question of whether or not this sampling will provide a true reflection of the view of the remaining 95% of the population. Secondly, 'sample bias' alone in the qualitative method does not provide the true picture. The findings at times may be influenced either knowingly or unknowingly, to a response that faces an anticipated outcome. Thirdly, and most importantly self-selection bias may arise where the researcher may ask the respondent to volunteer their views or in the desire of the researcher. In the Article, "The challenges of participant observations of cultural encounters. Within an ethnographic study" the writers Lopez-Dicastilloa, Belintxona (2014), acknowledged the challenges of biasness and reflexivity. They further state:

Ethnography has also challenges. Ethnographers need to be naïve when using ethnography, as the major tool is the researcher herself or himself. This in anthropology did not use to be a challenge as in traditional ethnography; the

researcher entered the field, for example, a village, as a stranger (Baillie, 1995).

In contrast, in the present study, the research setting will not be totally unfamiliar to the ethnographer. This can lead to potential bias; the avoidance of which largely relies on self-awareness on the researcher's behalf. In addition, the researcher might also feel negative toward the informants, but it must try to remain neutral. So, the use of the personal diary, recording feelings and emotions to check against possible bias, is highly recommended.

Another challenge in qualitative research is that sometimes it generates imposing and unwieldy datasets that are hard to deal with. It will be challenging while code and analyze bulky data after interviews and observations from the study site. Trustworthiness is also challenging in a qualitative study because it contains less straightforward than in a quantitative study because of the nature of the data. Also, empirical measurement is not possible because it has human input and understanding. John D. Brewer (1994)

"Ethnography has always been subject to criticism from quantitative sociologists, who accord it a minimal role, but it has recently come under attack from sociologists sympathetic to the method, whom themselves have considerable experience in its use. I call this the ethnographic critique of ethnography. This critique questions the reliability of ethnographic descriptions, and shows ethnographic texts to be artifacts, skillfully manufactured in order to construct their persuasive force."

The raw data obtained from the fieldwork needs analysis and interpretation. Thus, whatever whether that is a qualitative or quantitative data both has to undergo through data cleaning process which is professional termed is called data analysis. In research searching, evaluating, recognizing, coding, mapping, exploring and describing to provide underlying meanings to transform raw data. To analyze quantitative data is easier and processed through some statistical software. Whereas, qualitative data requires analytical examination and investigation of the information. Researcher's personal view and understanding on a particular subject or object determine the actual findings of the research. The interpretation phase may introduce bias from the researcher, as the researcher analyzes the data based on past experience (fieldwork), or unknowingly held assumptions. Qualitative data answers the 'why' and 'how' answers and it is an integral part of ethnographic study. However, the problem is, it collects subjective data; it takes a lot of time to collect data, and it is difficult to rightly represent the information. The researcher has a greater role in its interpretation. Sometimes researcher influence can have a negative effect on the collected data and unrecorded data can be disappeared.

➤ *Expectations and Importance of Respondents*

Academic research doesn't resolve the existing problems, but rather highlights the problems on the surface of the community. In the context of Nepal, it is mostly found that the respondent expects a researcher will resolve the

community issues that they are struggling on day-to-day life. This is a great problem that it is either a researcher who fails these people to understand or it is a natural tendency that these locals expect and at times demand from the researcher. And when the community realizes that nothing will be addressed there is a high possibility for participants to respond inaccurately and falsely to the questions that they are asked by the researcher. Which ultimately raises the validity and reliability of the research.

Respondents are treated as important actors in any research, and it is the same with ethnographic research. Respondents are the people of the targeted community who have been invited to participate in the particular study and have actually taken part in the study. During the question-answer session with the respondent, they first interpret the question and then recall the relevant facts. Formulate an answer and finally gives a verbal response. Respondents should be qualified (meeting an objective of the research designs) and willing to participate in the research. Therefore, the role of the respondent is important in qualitative research. Furthermore, Jones and Smith (2017) explain the challenges faced by the researchers while collecting first-hand data in the field. They state,

“Engaging with participants in the real world poses several challenges; first the researcher must decide whether to adopt an overt or covert approach to data collection and observation. In an overt approach, the participants know they are being observed, whereas in a covert approach the participants are unaware they are being observed.”

Many times, the different researcher enters the same community and frequent research is conducted asking the same questions. This creates frustration and in a long run, they either show reluctance to participate in any research or provide the wrong information to the researcher. The success of the ethnographic research is solely based on the willingness; and active participation of the respondents. And, an important component in research is always how respondents comprehend questions and how the interviewer handles the situation.

➤ *Other Concerns (Time Constraint, Economic Hardship, Geographical Obstruction, Extreme Climatic Condition, Tedious Fieldwork, Lacks of a Longitudinal Study, and External Factors Affecting the Community)*

Generally, ethnographic research is supposed to be the most in-depth research method. Where the researcher invests longer time at a research site. And observe what people are doing, saying, and interacting with each other. In a real sense, in it, ethnographers obtain a deep understanding of the population and cultural system in the broader context.

In order to execute real ethnographic research it cost you both money and time. Which at times is unaffordable to university students. Who are struggling and are burdened with financial problems. Many governments and even universities in some other countries have adopted a policy to provide financial support to conduct research and dissertation. But in our country, the government has failed to

provide adequate scholarship quota to these strugglers. If any provided are limited and are not accessible to every scholar. As a result, many researchers dropped out their remaining course and does not proceed further because of no money and time. The intensity of the problems is more found among ethnographic scholars, because of their intensive involvement in the field with the people.

From an ecological perspective, the geography of Nepal provides rich resources to carry out the research. However, the geographical diversity of the land also equally provides a challenge for the researcher. Geographically, our country is classified into three main regions: mountainous, hilly, and plain region. All these three constituents of extreme land structure and climatic conditions, at times, create unexpected challenges for a researcher. Since ethnographic research focuses its study on an indigenous, native and ethnic group. These populations are mostly found in difficult land structures, high mountainous regions, and close to forests and rivers (and to reach most of these places lacks transportation facilities). So, it is tiring and challenging to approach to such places and climates.

Ethnographic research includes tedious fieldwork. To gain cultural insight and social process every researcher has to immerse and spent quality time to understand the deeper meaning of cultural phenomena. Fieldwork is intellectually and technically challenging when the fieldwork is in a difficult environment – conflict, post-conflict and post-disaster area. In many a situation, it is seen that a researcher is misled or engulfed in emotion after entering the research site. Other challenges associated with the fieldwork are logistics and transportation; access and trust; barriers such as language and gender. Respondents hide data or provide misinformation and influence the participants in your study. In the field, researchers, also struggle with security and coping with stress. At times researcher ends up making friends with the participants. S/he feels sympathy and empathy with the respondents. In Ethnographic research fieldwork is important. But many times, the researchers do not reveal and acknowledge much about their fieldwork. It is found that Ethnographic studies do not incorporate a wide range of conventional ethnographic features and often result in less time spent in the field. They often engaged in narrow topics conducted in familiar surroundings and issues (Rashid, Caine, & Goez, 2015).

An attribute of culture is that it is acquired, transmitted, and dynamic, it can be learned and shared. In other words, the nature of the culture is changing, it is not stable. One of the challenges that is seen in ethnographic research under Anthropology is, it studies about particular context only at a time. It lacks longitudinal research that involves repeated observation and participation over a long period of time, sometimes even decades. To formulate deep understanding of human experiences over a long period of time, it is essential in anthropological research to longitudinal qualitative studies is always useful in ethnographic research as it tries to answer the question about the change that occurred between two-time duration, why, how and when the change has occurred and contextual

factor related to change. We know longitudinal research has its own limitations, however, for a holistic understanding of human behavior, it is significant to conduct longitudinal research even in ethnographic studies.

Ethnographic research focuses and studies on the inner factors, and limits the external factors affecting the community. External factors like economic institutions, political environment, and ecological issues are missed out in ethnographic research. This is challenging for ethnographers to interlinked these external components and study as a whole. And at the same time, one can't ignore the external agencies impacting the inner cultural practice within a community. So, both these components (inside and outside) that are responsible for the change in society have to study balancing both factors. This is challenging for all ethnographers in the future how these factors can be addressed while studying the ethnographic studies of a particular community.

V. DISCUSSION

From the critical lens, we can always discuss numerous subjects under ethnographic research. First of all, any anthropologist scholar willing to undertake this sort of detailed research has to have an inclusive understanding of the subject matter. With complete awareness and required skills on how its methodological approaches are implemented, an ethnographer should a step-by-step process. Since Ethnographic research is about people, special precautions, and formulating standard ethical guidelines are to be approved by the concerned institution and strictly followed. Selection of sample size and respondents is always an important turn determining the validity of the research. All qualitative researchers have to examine that sample size is a mostly criticized element in ethnographic research. A question that is always raised to ethnographers is whether a selected sample or respondent represents a whole population or not. A researcher has to justify such false assumptions through designing professionally in research design.

Then, follows fieldwork, which is obviously overburdening, however, this is a part and requirement in ethnographic research. We can't ignore the fact that proper, intensive, and close participation and observation have to make in order to dig out realistic information by selecting a suitable research site and by developing a rapport. Adequate time needs to spend on the field. The next important aspect of qualitative research lies in its interpretation and analysis of data. There is always a tendency (generated consciously or unconsciously) to manipulate the data in order to meet the desired outcome as set in the research question or objective. A good researcher prohibits such practices and always presents the real picture of the findings of the research.

VI. CONCLUSION

From the above studies, what can be drawn, as the conclusion is that, "Ethnographic research" in Anthropology is filled up with various challenges if not properly designed, managed, and conducted. Ethnographic research in itself is an effective method for collecting qualitative data under Anthropology. But its effectiveness and efficiency can be measured if its standard procedures and guidelines are systematically followed, keeping in mind the essence of the research. These days there is a growing trend among the researchers of social science and humanities to carry out ethnographic research through a qualitative approach. It is encouraging to an anthropologist that there is increased knowledge and resource in this field.

A researcher should be tactful, creative, and professional enough to convert the challenges and limitations that exist in ethnographic studies into opportunities. And at the same time, an ethnographer should be well-versed in the ethnographic methodology. Since it is a complex area of study, proper research can generate and outline desired results, but if handled improperly, the targeted object of the research will be messed. It is all up to a researcher as to how he has understood and perceives the whole ethnographic process.

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